

MAIZE COB AND CEREAL CHAFF: FEEDSTOCKS FOR ENERGY PRODUCTION

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ABSTRACT: Many EU projects affirm that there is significant potential to expand the share of energy & material production from biomass in a 2020-2030 timeframe in a sustainable way and without entering into conflict with food and feed security. Furthermore, all studies agree about the necessity to unlock the potential of underutilized agricultural resources to reach the planned European bio-economy goals. Agricultural residues like maize cob and grain chaff with an annual European availability of 9.6 Mt and 54.8 Mt respectively, represent an interesting underutilized amount of potential biomass for energy production. Moreover, the harvesting logistics of cob and chaff grain are supported by equipment already available in the market. Cob and chaff are used in different industrial fields but few studies have analyzed the potential as feedstock for industrial boilers to produce energy, separately or in combination with other biomass types. This is a preliminary study to investigate the physical and chemical characteristics of chaff grain and maize cob in order to verify their potential use in industrial boilers for the production of heat and electricity. Moisture and ash contents, ash melting point, heating value, and concentrations of C, H, N, S of cob and chaff were analyzed in order to evaluate the potential behavior as solid biofuel either as direct utilization or by mixing them with other biomass types.

Keywords: cereal chaff, maize cob, agricultural residues, characteristics, combustion.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to reduce the emissions of greenhouse gasses and bring down energy import dependency, the European Union has thus set ambitious 2020 indicative targets for the share of renewable energy in both total energy (20%) and electricity consumption [1]. Currently, around 4 % of the total primary energy consumption of the European Union is met from biomass, and it will become 13% in 2020. This makes biomass the most important renewable energy source, providing two thirds of the total energy produced from renewable [1].

For this to become reality biomass use will roughly have to double. In the short to medium run, agricultural residues could provide a remarkable amount of cellulosic biomass currently untapped that might contribute to the achievement of the renewable energy targets.

In fact, significant amounts of agricultural residues are generated from agricultural crop production and partially remain in the field after harvest. Maize and wheat are two of the most frequently planted crops throughout the world because of their high productivity for food, chemical purposes and livestock feed. Their by-products are the cobs and chaff. Maize cob is the central core of an ear of maize (*Zea mays* ssp.) and the part of the corn ear on which the kernels grow, and chaff is a mix of grain husk, weed seeds, and short pieces of straw. In Europe, the only maize cob and grain chaff could provide an annual biomass potential availability of 9.6 Mt and 54.8 Mt respectively [2,3].

However, they are both by-products usually left on the ground and not collected. Turning agricultural residues into valuable and cost-effective feedstocks greatly depends on the harvest technology. For chaff and cob, mature harvesting technologies are already available on the market [4,5]. In fact, in some countries, exist markets of chaff and cob that are used as absorbent for animal bedding, substrate in hydroponic cultivation, adsorbent for production of active carbon for water treatment, abrasive material for metal or wood surface

conditioning.

On the other hand, soil fertility decline is currently a key issue in Europe and sometimes faced with the utilisation of agricultural on-field residues. The removal of crop residues should be balanced against the environmental impact (soil erosion), maintenance of nutrients and soil organic matter levels, and preservation of productivity levels [6]. When considering the role of crop residue in the maintenance of soil productivity, maize cob (representing 15-20% content of maize stover) collection offers advantages when compared to the harvesting of the whole stover. Cobs have lower concentrations of several nutrients (N, P, K, S, and Ca) compared to stover fractions.

In some European regions, there are no markets or convenience to collect and use chaff and cob, and on-field burning results the most common method to dispose them of, and this represent the most impacting practice on global warming, human health, photochemical oxidation, acidification, and on eutrophication impact categories [7].

For this reason, the utilization of cob and chaff in large power plants designed to burn the biomass can permit to reduce the dependency to fossil fuels and reduce the greenhouse gasses emissions. Biomass does not add carbon dioxide to the atmosphere as it absorbs the same amount of carbon in growing as it releases when consumes as a fuel [8].

However, fuel properties and characteristics are important to boiler design and operation. Different boilers have unique design and fuel requirements.

Heating value, total ash and moisture content, ash melting point are all key parameters considered by the boiler designer. Some biomass products have unique utilization issues. The chemical behavior of biomass materials can be very different from each other.

This is a preliminary study to investigate the physical and chemical characteristics of cereal chaff and maize cob in order to verify their potential use in industrial boilers for the production of heat and/or electricity.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The aim of the work is to investigate the potential utilization of maize cob and cereal chaff as feedstock for industrial boilers in areas where these by-products are available but there are no market.

Five samples of wheat chaff and maize cob were randomly collected by the experimental fields of La Rochelle (France) and Marene (Cuneo, Italy) during showcases organized for the project Agroinlog [9].

The physic-chemical characterization of the cob and chaff were performed by the Biomass Group of D3A Department at the Polytechnic University of Marche (Ancona, Italy).

The analysis were conducted according to EN ISO standards. The moisture and ash contents, ash melting point (AMP), heating value, and concentrations of N, Cl, and S were analyzed.

The moisture content as received was determined according to the EN ISO 14774-2 [10]. The HHV was performed according to EN ISO 18125. The HHV represents the amount of thermal energy generated by the combustion of one kg of dry matter (considering the water in biomass at atmospheric pressure and at a liquid state of 15°C) [11].

The determination of the ash content was carried out according to the EN ISO 14775 [12]. The ash melting point was evaluated according to the UNI CEN/TS 15370-1 [13]. The nitrogen was obtained according to EN ISO 15104.

The chlorine and sulfur content was determined according to EN ISO 16994.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Whereas the moisture contents of most agricultural residues (as fired), are low, some residues such as bagasse are fired with 40–60 wt% moisture.

In most cases, the moisture contents of the residues are determined by the process of separating the residues from the crop product (like for coffee where the husk are removed after an industrial drying process) [14]. In the case of cereal chaff, the drying process happens naturally on the field and the moisture content during the harvesting results very low (Table I). In the case of the corn cob, the moisture content resulted about 40%.

Usually, biomass with moisture content > 40% are considered with high moisture content [8]. For this reason, maize cob can be considered at the limit.

Table I: Corn cob and cereal chaff comparison. Low Heating Value, Moisture and ash contents.

Biomass	Moisture		Ash		LHV	
	%w/w		%w/w		MJ/kg _{db}	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Corn cob	40.80	0.18	2.02	0.01	17.64	0.04
Wheat chaff	10.12	0.03	9.75	0.14	16.27	0.03

The more water content would result into lower fuel efficiency. The more water fuel contains would require bigger boiler volume resulting more expensive boiler. Furthermore, transportation of water is not feasible.

Moisture affects has a negative impact also on the cleaning of the boilers (e.g. acid condensation, fouling, sludging) by reducing the furnace temperature.

If the fuel contains sulfur and chlorine then the risk of corrosion of heat recovery unit, ID fan, ducting and chimney is higher [8].

The releases of alkali metals, chlorine and sulfur to the gas-phase may also lead to generation of significant amounts of aerosols (sub micron particles) along with relatively high emission of HCl and SO₂ [8]. Straw has been found to be one of the most corrosive type of biomass not previously encounter with combustion of fossil fuels [8]. However, our results showed that, unlike the wheat straw, the wheat chaff results with a low percentage of Chlorine and Sulfur (Table II). On the other hand, maize cob reported an higher amount of Chlorine.

Table II: Corn cob and cereal chaff Chlorine, Sulfure and Nitrogen contents.

Biomass	N		Cl		S	
	%w/w					
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Corn cob	0.75	0.01	0.27	0.01	0.02	0.00
Wheat chaff	0.73	0.04	0.04	0.00	0.04	0.01

The content of nitrogen (N) in biofuels is quite low with value normally less than 1% and is particularly high in cereals where it can reach 5% [11]. In chaff and cob, the nitrogen content resulted similar and in average equal to 0.74%.

The ash content varies from one residue to another.

High ash content is a characteristic that negatively affects the biomass energy content [15]. Ash is inorganic material that remains after the combustion of the fuel.

Increasing the amount of ash adversely affects the calorific value because it represents the fraction of the biomass that remains unburned [16] and also affects boiler performance. Finally, it affects also the boiler management costs because a high content of ash means more material to be disposed of as special waste [17].

For the combustion of agricultural residues with high ash contents, such as maize cob, consideration must be given to incorporate an efficient ash removal equipment from the flue gas to eliminate or reduce particulate pollution. In this way could be reduced ignition and combustion problems [18].

A peculiar ash problem, which is normally experienced during the combustion of some agricultural residues, is the low melting properties of the ash. This is due to the presence of very high contents of potassium oxide (K₂O) in some residues. The problems attributed to low melting temperatures of the ashes from these residues are scaling, fouling, and corrosion of the heat transfer surfaces as well as bed agglomeration in fluidized bed [14]. These phenomenon can significantly reduce the efficiency of the heat exchangers. Woody biomass with high ash melting point is thus essential to increase the productivity of the system and to reduce maintenance costs. Tests on herbaceous biomass such as reed canary grass show a melting temperature in all phases over 1,200°C up to about 1,250°C while for woody biomasses, such as birch and poplar, from 1,400°C up to about 1,500°C [28,29]. In a recent study [30], the ash melting point of *Arundo donax*, L. resulted 896°C.

From this research resulted a low ash content in cob (Table I) and high in chaff. On the other hand, cob showed lower ash melting point than chaff (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ash melting analysis of wheat chaff and corn cob. DT= Initial deformation temperature; ST= Softening temperature; HT= Hemispherical temperature; FT= Fluid temperature.

The results showed that the maize cob and cereal chaff parameters are outside the technical specification in direct burning. However, mixtures can compensate for the problems expected from the use of individual biomasses. Mixtures may allow to obtain a new fuel that would meet the specifications of EN-ISO 17225-6 (Solid biofuels - Fuel specifications and classes - Part 6: Graded non-woody pellets). This would bring economic and environmental benefits.

Future study would be necessary to investigate the combustion behavior of cob and chaff in different percentage mix in order to obtain a biofuel with better characteristics than the single row materials.

4 CONCLUSION

The aim of the work is to investigate the potential utilization of maize cob and cereal chaff as feedstock for industrial boilers in areas where these by-products are available but there are no market.

From the analysis can be speculate that the use of chaff and cobs to produce energy could bring environmental benefits in terms of reduced use of fertilizers (higher if biomass is buried), and reduced CO₂ emissions (replacing fossil fuels and avoiding open air field combustion).

Future studies should focus on identifying the most suitable mixtures of these raw materials with others to fulfill energy equipment requirements.

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7 LOGO SPACE

